

Mixed-ligand Complex Formation of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Zinc(II) with *N*-Benzenesulphonyl-*l*-cysteine as Primary Ligand and Bipyridine, Ethylenediamine and Glycinate as Secondary Ligands

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Equilibrium study on the complex formation of M^{2+} ions ($M = Co, Ni$ and Zn) with *N*-benzenesulphonyl-*l*-cysteine ($NBSCH_2$) in the presence of bipyridine, ethylenediamine, glycinate (B) indicates the formation of mixed-ligand complexes of the types $M(NBSC)(B)$, $M(H_{-1}NBSC)(B)$ and $M(H_{-1}NBSC)(OH)$, together with binary $M(NBSC)$ and $M(B)$ complexes. Formation constants of the complexes have been determined by potentiometric method at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium at a constant ionic strength, $I = 0.2 M$ ($NaNO_3$). Stability of the complexes has been correlated with the modes of coordination of $NBSC$, basicity of the B ligands and π -electron delocalisation in the metal-ligands bonds.

N-Benzenesulphonyl-*l*-cysteine, $C_6H_5SO_2NHCH(CH_2SH)COOH$ (hereafter, $NBSCCH_2$) having three potential metal binding sites, viz. $COOH$, $-SO_2NH-$ and SH showed ambidentism in its binary complexes with hard, borderline and soft metal ions¹⁻³. With a view to study the modes of coordination of this interesting ligand in mixed ligand complexes with typical (N,N) and (N,O) bidentate ligands, its complex formation with M^{2+} ions ($M = Co, Ni$ and Zn) in the presence of bipyridine (bipy), ethylenediamine (en) and glycinate (gly⁻) has been studied by potentiometric method in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium at a constant ionic strength, $I = 0.2 M$ ($NaNO_3$) at $25 + 0.1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

In the absence of M^{2+} ions the ligand $NBSCCH_2$ titrates as a diprotic acid. It gives two well-separated buffer regions corresponding to successive deprotonation of the $COOH$ and SH groups ($pK_{COOH}^H, 4.35$; $pK_{SH}^H, 10.99$). The sulphonamide ($-SO_2NH-$) group remains neutral in the absence of M^{2+} ions. Metal ion coordination with the $-SO_2NH-$ group takes place normally at the N atom with or without release of the sulphonamide proton¹⁻³. Having three types of coordinating groups, viz. hard ($COOH$), borderline ($-SO_2NH-$) and soft (SH), the ligand $NBSCCH_2$ shows remarkable bonding features in its binary complexes with different metal ions. It binds the soft Ag^+ ion as a monodentate ligand with the SH group, the $COOH$ and $-SO_2NH-$ groups remain uncoordinated⁴. It binds Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Hg^{2+} as a (N,S) bidentate ligand using S^- and $-SO_2NH-$ groups, the COO^- group remain uncoordinated^{2,3,5}. With Zn^{2+} , however, it provides terdentate (O,N,S) coordination using the COO^- , $-SO_2NH-$ and S^- groups¹.

Species distribution curves (Figs. 1-3) of the ternary $M^{2+}/NBSCCH_2/B$ systems ($M = Co, Ni$ and Zn) indicate the formation of $M(NBSC)(B)$ complexes according to equi-

libria (1-5).

Charges are omitted for clarity. Coordination by the ligand

Fig. 1. Species distribution curves of $M^{2+}/NBSC/bipy$ systems of (a) $M = Ni$ and (b) $M = Zn$: (1) $NBSC$, (2) $M(bipy)^{2+}$, (3) $M(NBSC)(bipy)$, (4) $M(H_{-1}NBSC)(bipy)$, (5) $M(H_{-1}NBSC)(bipy)(OH)^2$

Fig. 2. Species distribution curves of $M^{2+}/NBSC/en$ systems of (a) $M = Ni$ and (b) $M = Zn$: (1) $NBSC$, (2) enH_2^{2+} , (3) enH^+ , (4) M^{2+} , (5) $M(NBSC)$, (6) $M(en)^{2+}$, (7) $M(NBSC)(en)$, (8) $M(H_{-1}NBSC)(en)^+$, (9) $M(H_{-1}NBSC)(en)(OH)^2$

Fig. 3. Species distribution curves of $M^{2+}/NBSC/gly^-$ systems (a) $M = Ni$ and (b) $M = Zn$: (1) $NBSC$, (2) $glyH^+$, (3) M^{2+} , (4) $M(NBSC)$, (5) $M(gly)^-$, (6) $M(NBSC)(gly)^-$, (7) $M(H_{-1}NBSC)(gly)^{2-}$, (8) $M(H_{-1}NBSC)(gly)(OH)^{3-}$

ion $NBSC^{2-}$, in all these mixed-ligand complexes is found to take place at such pH values, where the $COOH$ group of $NBSC$ is completely deprotonated and the ligand exists in the $NBSC^-$ form. Eqm. (1) and (5) involve deprotonation of the SH group of $NBSC^-$. Thus the COO^- group of the resulting $NBSC^{2-}$ ion remains uncoordinated in $M(NBSC)(B)$ complexes with all the three metal ions and all the three B ligands.

$M(NBSC)(bipy)$ complexes are formed exclusively according to eqm. (1) (Fig. 1). $M(NBSC)(en)$ complexes with Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} are formed according to eqms. (1) and (5), whereas the corresponding Zn^{2+} complex is formed according to eqms. (2) and (3) (Fig. 2). $M(NBSC)(gly)^-$ complexes with Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} are formed according to eqms. (1) and (2) and the corresponding Zn^{2+} complex according to eqm. (4) (Fig. 3). Species distribution curves for Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} systems are only presented for brevity and comparison.

With rise of pH (>7), the $M(NBSC)(B)$ complexes successively lose two protons. The first step deprotonation of $M(NBSC)(B)$ complexes of Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} is accompanied by intense colouration of the solution^{2,3} which is obviously due to deprotonation (1) $\rightleftharpoons$ (2) of the coordinated sulphonamido group according to

Acidity of the sulphonamide proton is known to increase upon metal ion coordination¹⁻⁵. In case of $NBSC$ com-

plexes, this increase is relatively sharp due to increase of electronegativity of M through back-donation in the $M(\pi) \rightarrow S(\pi)$ bond (3),

Such metal promoted deprotonation of the sulphonamide group in $M(NBSC)(B)$ complexes may be represented by eqm. (6),

where, $H_{-1}NBSC^{3-}$ in the resulting complexes stands for the fully deprotonated $NBSC$ ligand species, $C_6H_5SO_2\bar{N}-CH(CH_2\bar{S})CO\bar{O}$. Subsequent deprotonation of these $M(H_{-1}NBSC)(B)$ complexes takes place at $pH > 9$ without any remarkable change of colour of the solution of the Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} complexes. This obviously indicates the deprotonation of a molecule of coordinated H_2O in these $M(H_{-1}NBSC)(B)$ complexes, to produce the quaternary hydroxo complexes, $M(H_{-1}NBSC)(B)(OH)$ according to eqm. (7),

Replacement of a H_2O ligand with OH^- ion does not change the strength of the ligand field around the Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions to a significant extent, consequently there is practically no change in the electronic spectra of these complexes with rise of pH above 9.

Stability of ternary complexes are characterised by their $\log \beta_M^{M(NBSC)(B)}$ and $\Delta \log K_M$ values⁶ which correspond to the equilibria (5) and (2) respectively. On the other hand, stability of quaternary hydroxo complex are characterised by the deprotonation constants, $K_{M(H_{-1}NBSC)(B)(H_2O)}^H$ of the corresponding aqua complexes⁷ (eqm. 7).

$M(H_{-1}NBSC)(B)$ and $M(H_{-1}NBSC)(B)(OH)$ complexes of Zn^{2+} are formed with all the three B ligands, *bipy*, *en* and *gly*⁻. With Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} only the sulphonamide deprotonated complexes, $M(H_{-1}NBSC)(B)$ are formed in small amounts, the quaternary hydroxo complexes $M(H_{-1}NBSC)(B)(OH)$ are not identified in the complexation equilibria (Figs. 1-3).

Stability of ternary $M(NBSC)(B)$ complexes in regard to the B ligands is found to follow the order: $en > bipy > gly^-$ for Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} , and the order: $bipy > en > gly^-$ for Zn^{2+} . Lower stability of *gly*⁻ complexes arise from the softening of the M^{2+} ions due to coordination by the thiolate (S^-) sulphur atom. As a result, the M^{2+} ions prefer to form stronger bonds with a (N,N) ligand system such as *bipy* and *en* than with harder (N,O) ligand system such as *gly*⁻. Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions, due to coordination by strongly π -acidic thiolate sulphur atom, tend to form stronger bonds with a ' σ -donor only' ligand, such as *en* than with a ' σ -donor-cum- π -acceptor' ligand such as *bipy*. This is possibly the reason for higher stability of ternary $M(NBSC)(en)$ complexes over the corresponding $M(NBSC)(bipy)$ complexes

with Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions. Higher stability of ternary $\text{M}(\text{NBSC})(\text{B})$ complexes with Zn^{2+} ion than the corresponding complexes of Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} suggests higher selectivity of Zn^{2+} for the thiolate sulphur ligand. This uniqueness of Zn^{2+} is quite relevant to importance as a cofactor in many enzymic reactions⁸. Metal promoted deprotonation constants of the $-\text{SO}_2\text{NH}-$ group (eqm. 6) and deprotonation of the coordinated H_2O molecules (eqm. 7) correlate nicely with the formation constants $\beta_{\text{M}(\text{NBSC})(\text{B})}^{\text{M}}$ of the ternary $\text{M}(\text{NBSC})(\text{B})$ complexes.

Experimental

The ligand NBSCCH_2 was prepared and purified according to the reported procedure⁹. All the other reagents were of AnalaR grade and their solutions were prepared in double-distilled CO_2 -free water and purified ethanol¹⁰. Metal (M^{2+}) nitrate solutions were standardised by combined ion-exchange separation, complexometric and acid-base titrations¹¹. Following series of solutions were prepared for potentiometric measurements : (a) 0.01 M HNO_3 ; (b), (a) + 0.001 M M^{2+} nitrate; (c), (a) + 0.002–0.01 M ligand (NBSCCH_2 or bipyH_2^{2+} or enH_2^{2+} or glyH_2^+); (d), (c) + 0.001–0.002 M M^{2+} nitrates; (e), (a) + 0.002 M M^{2+} nitrates + 0.002 M NBSCCH_2 + 0.002 M bipyH_2^{2+} or enH^+ or glyH_2^+ . Initial volume of each solution was 25 ml in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium. Requisite amounts of NaNO_3 were placed in each solution to have a fixed ionic strength $I = 0.2 \text{ M}$. All the solutions were allowed to attain equilibrium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ (thermostated) and titrated with a carbonate-free¹² standard 0.125 M NaOH solution, prepared in the same solvent, having the desired ionic strength maintained at the same temperature. pH measurements were made with a Systronics 335 pH meter (accuracy ± 0.01 pH) using a special glass electrode (pH = 1–14) in conjunction with an SCE. The pH meter was calibrated using aqueous buffer solutions of pH 4.0, 7.0 and 9.2 making appropriate correction for temperature. Analytical hydrogen ion concentrations at different pH values were obtained by the usual procedure using the pH titration data of solution (a) after incorporating corrections¹³ for the use of mixed solvent. Duplicate titrations were carried out to ascertain the reproducibility of data and also to check whether polynuclear complexes were formed.

Formation constants of metal-ligand complexes were evaluated by executing the computer programme SCOGS^{14,15} with the aid of a PC-XT computer system. The binary constants obtained from literature^{1–3, 16, 17} were re-determined under the experimental condition and used as input data for the calculation of ternary constants. As the pH range of complex formation was close to the pH range of hydrolysis of M^{2+} (aq.) ions in each case, the formation of the hydroxo species such as $\text{M}(\text{OH})^+$, $\text{M}(\text{OH})_2$, $\text{M}(\text{NBSC})(\text{OH})^-$, $\text{M}(\text{B})(\text{OH})$ etc. were also considered in

calculating the ternary constants. Complexation equilibria were then elucidated with the aid of the species distribution curves (Figs. 1–3) obtained as computer output. Results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND BINARY, TERNARY AND QUATERNARY CONSTANTS OF $\text{M}^{2+}/\text{NBSC}/\text{B}$ SYSTEMS ($\text{M} = \text{Co}, \text{Ni}$ AND Zn ; $\text{B} = \text{bipy}, \text{en}$ AND gly^-)*

Temp. = 25° , ethanol-water : 50% (v/v), $I = 0.2 \text{ M}$ (NaNO_3)

(a) Proton-ligand constants :

	NBSCCH_2	bipyH_2^{2+}	enH_2^{2+}	glyH_2^+
$\text{p}K_2^{\text{H}}$	4.35	0.70	6.83	2.97
$\text{p}K_1^{\text{H}}$	10.99	3.47	9.02	8.79

(b) Hydrolysis constants of M^{2+} (aq.) ions.

	Co^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Zn^{2+}
$\text{p}K_{\text{M}}^{\text{H}}$	7.36	7.62	9.44
$\text{p}K_{\text{M}}^{2\text{H}}$	15.51	15.88	16.42

(c) Binary constants, $\log K_{\text{M}(\text{ligand})}^{\text{M}}$ values :

$\log K_{\text{M}(\text{NBSC})}^{\text{M}}$	6.11	6.59	8.96
$\log K_{\text{M}(\text{bipy})}^{\text{M}}$	6.50	6.65	5.90
$\log K_{\text{M}(\text{en})}^{\text{M}}$	6.54	7.33	5.52
$\log K_{\text{M}(\text{gly})}^{\text{M}}$	6.19	6.23	5.13

(d) Ternary constants, $\log \beta_{\text{M}(\text{NBSC})(\text{B})}^{\text{M}}$ values (eqm. 5) :

bipy	12.69	13.34	14.98
en	13.25	14.02	14.08
gly	11.10	12.72	13.94

(e) $\Delta \log K_{\text{M}}$ values (eqm. 2) :

bipy	8.08	0.10	0.12
en	0.60	0.10	0.42
gly^-	-0.20	-0.10	-0.15

(f) Sulphonamide deprotonation constants, $\text{p}K_{\text{M}}^{\text{H}}(-\text{SO}_2\text{NH}-)$ (eqm. 6) :

bipy	11.49	11.50	8.52
en	11.50	10.60	8.70
gly	11.60	11.50	8.80

(g) Deprotonation constant, $\text{p}K_{\text{M}(\text{H}-1)\text{NBSC}(\text{B})}^{\text{H}}$ (H_2O) of coordinated H_2O (eqm. 7) :

bipy	11.50	12.00	9.60
en	12.60	13.10	9.80
gly	12.70	12.40	9.90

*Limits of error in the constants : $\pm(0.02-0.04)$ in log unit.

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